

Sustainable Interior Lighting Design

Sara Sotoodeh* , Faraz Khojasteh Far**

1. Bachelor of Civil Engineering, Sadjad University of Technology, Mashhad, Iran;
Eng.sutude@gmail.com
2. Bachelor of Architecture, Islamic Azad University(Tehran North branch), Tehran, Iran;
Faraz.khojasteh@aol.com

Abstract

The universal growth of interest over the last 3 decades in the idea of 'sustainability' or 'sustainable development' has brought challenges with it to the way in which impact assessment has been routinely conceived. The lighting design addresses multiple sustainable issues that can be recognized in particular projects. There are two main reasons to make lighting system sustainable. First, lighting energy use in buildings is high. The second reason relates to the fact that in the main categories of energy consumption, the only calculable and stable demand is related to lighting. In this article, by review the history of Iran architecture and historical overview of the role of mathematics in architecture, we categorized design factors to improve interior lighting design sustainability.

Keywords: Sustainability, Lightening Design, Interior Design, Historical Iran Architecture.

1. Introduction

1-1 Sustainability: The pervasive growth of interest over the last 3 decades in the idea of 'sustainability' or 'sustainable development' has brought with it challenges to the way in which impact assessment has been traditionally conceived. Designed originally in the late 1960s and early 1970s to focus on the environmental impacts of proposed projects, impact assessment has recently been reassessed by scholars to take account of sustainable development [1]-[5]. There has been a following call for the development of 'sustainability assessment' procedures that would contribute to the shift towards a more sustainable society. Available definitions of sustainability assessment include:

- "Sustainability assessment is...a tool that can help decision-makers and policy-makers decide what actions they should take and should not take in an attempt to make society more sustainable" [6].

•Sustainability assessment aims to ensure that “plans and activities make an excellent contribution to sustainable development” [5].

1-2 Lighting Design: One of the most important tools that can enhance the design and architecture of places is the proper design of lighting systems which can influence the value of the space that is the most non-material but perceivable nature element of sacred places. Lighting design is almost a new part of the process of construction. Many of the principles and standards needed for lighting come from architecture and engineering. Yet, because of the rapid changes in lighting technology and design technique, exclusive lighting issues must be addressed by the lighting designer [7].

1-3 Sustainable Lighting Design: Lighting design addresses several sustainable issues that can be considered in projects: daylight utilization, lighting controls, energy efficiency, materials, light pollution, and light trespass. All of these issues have significant impacts on the project budget that can best be evaluated with a life-cycle cost analysis [8]. There are two main reasons to make lighting system sustainable. First, lighting energy use in buildings is high. Lightening is a high percentage of total power consumption followed by other equipment. The second reason relates to the fact that there are three main categories of energy consumption: lighting equipment, HVAC equipment, and power equipment, and out of these three, the only predictable and durable demand is related to lighting. The lighting system in a building is usually on for a consistent number of hours while HVAC equipment tends to consume a different amount of power every day depending upon daily temperature [9]. In this article by using the history of Iran architecture and historical overview of the role of mathematics in architecture, we categorized how to make interior lighting design sustainable.

2. Historical Overview

2-1 Aina-Kari: is a kind of interior decoration made by Iranian artists who assemble remarkably cut mirrors together in geometric, calligraphic, or foliage forms in the 17th century [10]. This initiates a beautiful luminous surface covered with complex facets, reflecting light as complex abstract patterns or sparkling reflections. Beside their decorative use, this art is used as a strong durable cover for an interior space of a building. **Figure 1**

Figure 1 : Saadabad Historical Complex, Tehran, Iran. *Source: sadmu.ir*

2-2 Mathematics Role: It is well known that the vital science of forms and their order geometry contributes to the process of composition and designing in architecture. Evidently, composition in architecture starts with elements and their relations. Plus, Geometry can contribute to this process by dealing with geometric figures and forms as elements as well as proportions, angles, and transformations as relations between them [11]. Structures express general systems of order in various scientific disciplines, derived from the Latin notion “structure” which means joining together in order. Mathematics can be seen as a general science of structures regarding to systems of elements and their relations or applications. Further, fractal geometry, which certainly has many operations in architectural design, is the study of mathematical shapes that display a cascade of endless and identical details as one observes them more closely [12].

In fact, the relationship between architecture and geometry starts with the notion of harmony as the principle for all sciences and creations. The analysis of the ancient apprehension of harmony shows the geometrical root and the noted idea of this concept for all sciences and designing education [13].

3. Literature Research

3-1 Daylight concept: Utilizing daylight to provide the light in the building has the benefit of reducing lighting energy requirements while improving the quality of the indoor spaces. However, it also requires a significant increase in design time and coordination. This strategy may require additional modeling to ensure that daylight is provided without glare or increased heat gain [9]. **Figure 2**

Figure 2 : Building Lobby (daylighted). Photo: J. Benya

Daylighting is an exquisite light source for approximately all interior spaces. The amount of available daylight varies according to time of day, time of year, weather, pollution levels, and so on. The maximum amount of daylight is about 10,000 foot-candles on a sunny summer day. For energy efficiency in buildings, however, only about 5% of the daylight, or a peak of about 500 footcandles, should be allowed into a building; more will generate so much heat that energy will be wasted in air conditioning. The color of daylight varies as well. The color temperature of the setting sun is as low as 2000K, and the normal sun-and-sky color temperature at noon on a sunny day is 5500#6000K. The cold blue light from the winter north sky is over 10,000K. The color quality (CRI) is excellent [7]. **Figure 3**

Real Light Sources

Figure 3 : Color Spectra [7]

3-1-1 Top lighting: One of the most common ways to introduce daylight is through skylights and other means of top lighting. Top lighting acts like direct electric lighting does by radiating light downward. Principles commonly used for designing electric lighting systems can also be used for top lighting, which is the easiest form of daylighting and is relatively unaffected by site orientation and adjacent buildings. If a large area of the building is not near a window, consider top-light skylights in one-story buildings or the top floor of multistory buildings. Simple top-light skylights should occupy 3% to 5% of the total roof area to provide adequate levels of interior lighting[7].

3-1-2 Side lighting: employs vertical fenestration, usually windows, to introduce natural light. Unlike top lighting, side lighting tends to introduce light that can be too bright relative to the room surfaces, sometimes causing glare. However, the desirable view provided by windows usually makes glare an acceptable side effect [7]. **Table 1**

Table 1: Daylighting Categories [7], [8]

Toplighting concepts		Skylight		permits direct solar and sky radiation through a fenestrated aperture.
		Clerestory		produces both direct and indirect lighting by introducing light through a vertical clerestory window. Depending on the adjacent roof, some of the light may be reflected downward by the ceiling into space.
		Sawtooth Clerestory		produces both direct and indirect lighting but, by bouncing a high percentage off the adjacent slanted ceiling, increases the amount of downward light and can minimize the amount of direct light.
		Monitor or Double Clerestory		permits abundant daylight, especially in buildings where solar orientation or weather does not permit the sawtooth or other more unusual designs.
Sidelighting concepts		Soffit overhang		Overhang soffits provide a limited amount of shading and are best employed on the south façade (northern hemisphere) of the building.
		Awning		Awnings or other extended shades offer additional protection and are generally needed on the east and west facades of the building.
		Light shelf		A light shelf provides both shading and indirect lighting for space, increasing the amount of daylight depth penetration. It is most effective on the south façade.

3-2 Mirror: Mirrors can't create light, only reflect it. Typically, much of the light from an electric light is absorbed by the walls of a room and a lot is also reflected. A light source mostly only radiates a certain amount of energy, so we can dispense with the idea of solving the world's energy problems with mirrors. If you shine a light into a mirror, you simply divert the energy in another direction. If a mirror is behind the light source such as a table lamp, the mirror only reflects the light which would otherwise have been absorbed by the wall. There is more light in the room, to be sure but it is wasting. To add more light to the room, you would have to raise the number of light waves being emitted. The reflection only changes the way of the waves, not the amount or intensity of the light [14].

3-3 Window Design: The application of the IGP shading screen as an environmental solution to solve daylight usability issues concerning energy consumption levels of cooling load in an EDS [15]. A six-point star IGP shading screen was selected to be tested parametrically, was adopted in this study where the new geometry should always be topologically identical to the starting point of the variations [16]. **Figure 4**

Figure 4 : Fixed topology parametric variations on a six-point star IGP [16]

The cell is the basic unit for the pattern, and the fundamental unit in the cell is the group of geometrical elements with non-repeating components [17]. **Figure. 5** A total number of 12 cases were tested under the fixed topology method as follows [16]:

IGP cell grid: diameter = 35 cm (fixed)

IGP fundamental unit (F): 4 cases (variable)

Thickness (T): T1 = 2.5 cm , and T2 = 5.0 cm (variable)

Depth (D): D1 = 2.5 cm, and D2 = 5.0 cm (variable)

Figure 5 : IGP parametric variables F, T, D [16]

Investigations presented a retrofitting method to achieve sufficient daylighting levels and increase energy efficiency in an educational space. It showed the significance of using IGP shading screens for better daylighting and energy performances [16].

3-4 Material: The mercury content of fluorescent, induction and HID light sources poses an environmental threat when sent to a landfill or incinerator. By law, commercial and other facilities must recycle these light sources. This cost must be considered when developing a life-cycle cost analysis [8].

4. Research Findings

To intake the energy-saving profits of daylighting, electric lights must be switched off or dimmed. This can be designed in different ways.

- Equal hand-operated switching or dimming to encourage the user to turn off or dim electric lights
- An automatic photoelectric device in each day-lighted zone that either switches off lights during daylight periods or dims lights in proportion to the amount of daylight
- An automatic photoelectric system that dims or switches off lighting systems throughout a building in response to daylight
- An automatic time-of-day control system, preferably with astronomic time functions, that switches or dims lights according to a fixed solar schedule each approach has merit. It is generally agreed that switching lights is the least expensive but dimming lights are the most desired. Step dimming has been found troublesome in many situations.

The use of both electric light and daylight often increases the need of whether the electric light source should match the natural light. Generally, applying an electric light source that is appropriate independent of daylight is probably best. To match daylight, a light source of very high color temperature is needed; this light would probably appear unusually cool as interior illumination at night.

When integrating electric and natural light, it is common to want to illuminate a skylight to imitate daylight at night, but this approach should be pursued carefully, if at all. Uplighting a skylight tends to send light through the glass and into the sky, wasting both the light and the energy consumed in creating it. What little light is reflected tends to create glare. However, illuminating the skylight well and splay can be effective. The goal is to create the illusion of sky-lighting without trying to match the illumination level [7].

One of the key challenges to greater renewable electricity supplies is the temporal mismatch between non-dispatchable renewable sources and peaks in electricity demand. Besides, increased electrification coupled with the de-carbonization of electricity generation is likely to increase the scale of demand peaks. This could turn to compulsion for investment in carbon-intensive peaker generation or capital intensive storage capacity as well as additional transmission and distribution network capacity which may then be substantially underutilized. Although major effort has been devoted to testing a range of demand response interventions to decrease or shift utilization, less attention has been given to the ability of certain appliances to lastingly reduce demand at peak through energy efficiency [18].

Electrification and renewable electricity generation are considered to be the two pillars of a low-carbon energy transition [19]-[21] because an increase in the share of renewable electricity sources has significant scope to diminish energy-related greenhouse gas emissions [22]. After all, renewables collectively constitute a less predictable generation resource [23].

Conclusion

In this article, we showed interior lighting can improve the energy saving of the building and categorized the main design factors to create sustainable design lighting. We categorized the sustainable lighting design's factors into 2 groups: 1)Interior design 2)Material design.

The interior design consists of using proper daylight concept and using mirrors in proper locations to save light waste to use less light and save more energy. On the other hand, the material design consists of designing windows and applying suitable lamps for sustainable design. **Table 2**

Table 2: Factors categories

<i>Sustainable Interior Lighting Design</i>			
Interior Design		Material Design	
Maximum Daylight Saving	Applying Mirrors in Proper Locations	IGP Window Design	Using Energy Efficient Lamps

To use the daylighting concept, the solution is different project-to-project. It depends on the plan, orientations, etc. We offer using top lighting design and side lighting design in the design of a building plan which plays an important role in energy saving. **Figure.6** On the other hand, applying mirrors depends on each space can be different but it is important to use it in proper locations to reduce the light loss in the building. As we investigate on IGP windows, using this pattern in design can be a proper way to make our lighting design sustainable. The other factor we mentioned in the second category, proper lamps for sustainability is the benchmark factor. Which are categorized as 1)Mercury content, 2)Recycling, and 3)Light source life.

Figure 6 : Potential energy savings from combining appropriate lighting technologies [18]

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